

Analyzing the effects of prevalence rate of postural and ergonomic abnormalities among computer users

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ABSTRACT

Computer usage is an indispensable part of human being lives. Therefore in this study we are analyzing the prevalence rate of posture and ergonomic disorders and abnormality of computer users. this research was historical and descriptive that was performed on the 160 students who had three years of experience working with computers. Data was collected via researcher questionnaire with high levels of validity and reliability and was analyzed by SPSS version 21. Findings from the research showed that 85 % of complication neck hyperlordosis, 90% of lowered shoulders, 70 percent of kyphosis pectoral, 65% posterior tilt of pelvic, 40% of genovarum and genovalgum, 30% complication ankle deviation that were common among students . neck hyperlordosis, lowered shoulders and genovarum and genovalgum are the most posture and ergonomic disorders and abnormality of computer users that were came into being for lack of physical activity due to continuous exertion and neglecting principles of ergonomic during computer working

Keywords: diseases and disorders, musculoskeletal, computer users

INTRODUCTION

What posture committee Academy of Orthopedic Surgeons thinks of body is the relative arrangement of the body parts toward one to another and good physical condition is defined as a form of muscular and skeletal balance which has proper alignment with body segments, so that we need the least amount of energy to maintain aimed body condition. The advantage of optimal physical condition is that puts minimal stress on the body's tissues (1, 2). Any changes in the relative arrangement of the different parts of the body are abnormality or defective physical condition which be accompanied with stress or too much pressure on tissues and body structures (1, 3). The postural abnormality which is caused by environmental stimuli is often a reversible or modifiable one (4). This has happened also due to the mechanization of life and using body less and the damaging effects caused by body immobility in one hand and in the other hand because of paying more attention to modern man, they made life better and easier and more stylish (5) while many people are doing activities such as working with the computer for long hours on a fixed and inappropriate posture and the issue has high prevalence rate (6). Reports show that working hours of people from 1997 to 2003 from 5.9 hours per day has reached to 14.6 hours and this upward trend still continues which had various side effects such as muscle disorders, headaches and neck pain (7, 8). With the advancement of science and technology and efforts to accelerate tasks and administrative tasks, using computer has becoming an integral part of people's lives. During the past two decades the use of computers has been increasing to the global level (9). For example, the number of desktop computers in

2006 in a developed country such as the USA was around 240 million and in a developing country like Iran it was seven million (10). According to conducted research long-term use of computer can cause skeletal - muscle problems in areas of the upper part of body, especially the neck, shoulder, arm, wrist and fingers (10-14). Millions of computer users all around the world are exposed to the risk of pain in different organs. Studies have shown that there is a relation between working with computer and raising painful disorders (15-17).

Controlling and maintaining postural status and the ability to maintain stability in body parts and respond to forces are threatening body structure. Body central nervous system to maintain the balance has the ability to respond to all of the inputs with suitable outputs. Musculoskeletal system must have required range of activities that is fit to certain activities. Shortening and muscle weakness due to poor prolonged posture, can cause contraction and spasm (2). Morouri in a large research estimated the prevalence of musculoskeletal diseases among keyboard users of 9% to 50%, while in control group it was 4.5% to 17%. The Bureau of Labor Statistics of America estimated the number of injuries resulting from repetitive tasks like typing and working with computer in 1997 and it was 92576 cases that 55% of them were involved with wrist (19). Ehsani et al (2013) showed that there is significant relationship between long-term work with a computer and hyperlordosis and the risk of neck pain in people who worked with computers for more than 3 hours a day is 5.52 times to people who work with computer less than 3 hours (20).

Among Iranian students according to the situation and the need

to use computers, long-term use of computers has become common and many of these people suffer from pain caused by postural disorders. Analyzing the factors that influencing these disorders can have an important strategy in the prevention and treatment of such pain and health promotion, in other hand few studies conducted on the most common and long terminjuries of computer users in our country, and also considering that such a study has not been conducted in the city of Mashhad, this study was conducted with the aim of determining the prevalence of postural abnormalities of computer users among engineering students at Ferdowsi University of Mashhad.

METHODOLOGY

This is a descriptive-survey study and time wise is after happening and retrospective and the purpose is functional. The sample members are with the average age of $20/06 \pm 4/93$, height $163/26 \pm 7/27$ and weight $65/59 \pm 9/01$ and body mass index equal to $24/80 \pm 2/99$. Data was collected by researcher questionnaire that consisted of two parts and was analyzed. The first part consisted of information such as age, weight, height, history of working with computers and second part was asking questions about sample members' injury. Cronbach's alpha test was used to evaluate its internal compliance. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.80 that reflects relatively high reliability and acceptable questionnaire. The reliability of questionnaire was evaluated by pretest – posttest agreement and it was 0.73 to 0.88 which is considered as normal. The sample was consisted of 160 students of the Faculty of Engineering of Ferdowsi University of Mashhad who were volunteers. Entering criteria was consisted of an average of three years of experience using computers and five hours of working with computer time per day, it need to mentioned that people who were injured due to accident or trauma were excluded. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data, calculate the mean and standard deviation and charts and all of them were analyzed in SPSS 21.

RESULTS

The distributed frequency and characteristics of participants in the study are presented in Table (1). Findings from the research showed that 85 % of complication neck hyperlordosis, 90% of lowered shoulders, 70 % of kyphosis pectoral, 65% posterior tilt of pelvic, 40% of genovarum and genovalgum, 30% complication ankle deviation that were common among students .

DISCUSSION

The results showed that complication neck hyperlordosis, lowered shoulders, kyphosis pectoral, posterior tilt of pelvic, genovarum and genovalgum, complication ankle deviation are common postural abnormalities and disorders among students. In a study that was done by Bastani and Lahmi also most injuries have been reported in the neck, back, shoulder, respectively 53%, 48% and 12% (15). Comparing these two studies shows that the highest prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders among computer users is in the neck, back, waist and shoulder. All this damages occur due to negligence and lack of attention to the correct principles and desired standards that

must be considered both in making computers and how to use them that is unfortunately has been ignored. In some studies there was a significant relationship between unusual head and body position at work includes: sitting down with twisted body or neck bent and complaining of neck and shoulder pain (21). It was also stated that holding neck while bending forward and working long hours in a same position is significantly related to neck pain (21). In a study that was conducted on 150 computer users in San Francisco, America, showed significant relationship between longer hours working and making fewer decisions with musculoskeletal disorders (22) which is consistent with this study because student users also mentioned long and ongoing hours working with computer as one of the reason for musculoskeletal disorders. In Germany, Sudan, Denmark and Lebanon female computer users compared to men, had reported higher neck and shoulder pain which this gender differences in reported pain can be because women tend more to do repetitive tasks more than men. While men do not desire to sit for long hours, in addition because of women are doing house chores and taking care of children are more opposed to stress comparing to men (23-25).

Many studies had analyzed injuries and abnormalities resulting from the use of devices such as computers and laptops which the study of Biswas et al (2012) can be mentioned. In this study which used both male and female members, complications of thoracic kyphosis and posterior pelvic tilt as a result of the constant and poor postural occurred more and these disorders were more common among female (26). Also Ger et al (2006) has studied and reported disorders such as neck hyperlordosis, genovarum and genovalgum knee and ankle deviation as a result of daily activities such as reading and working with computers in the company's financial staff (12). However it was shown in previous studies the complications of thoracic kyphosis in the hands of the person in the forward mode doing that for a long time (22, 27-29). Neck hyperlordosis happens because of happening person's hands lean forward mode make disorder in person body to coordinate and the achievement of facilitate structural actions (30, 31). However, if the person developing hyperlordosis have enough potential toward that suffers from this disorder severely (32). Due to this issue, the implementation of intervention of ergonomics programs seems necessary in the workplace.

CONCLUSION

The complication of neck hyperlordosis, lowered shoulders, kyphosis pectoral, posterior tilt of pelvic, genovarum and genovalgum, complication ankle deviation are common postural abnormalities and disorders among students and the reason is lack of physical activity due to the constant use of computer and not following ergonomic principles in working time. For treatment of these injuries people should use stretching practices and special exercises for organs which are involved with the working with computer, offered by instructors and physical education and sport trainers and the appropriate work station design, training and informing computer users of ergonomic principles when they are working with computers so they can prevent injury and chronic fatigue

in their body organs.

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